

IN VESSEL MELT RETENTION 0D MODEL FOR INTEGRAL PRESSURIZED WATER REACTORS

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ABSTRACT

The In Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR) strategy developed for Light Water Reactors (LWR) is an appealing solution for the mitigation of many Severe Accident (SA) scenarios. Allowing the corium to remain in the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV), significantly reduces the stresses on the containment. This approach is typical of innovative reactors like the AP1000 and the Hualong One, both GW-size Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR). In this paper, the IVMR application for integral PWR (iPWR) is investigated. These kinds of reactors are characterized by an electrical power output generally lower than 300 MWe, an integral layout and the use of passive safety systems. During a postulated accidental sequence that leads to fuel melting, the molten corium relocates down to the lower plenum of the RPV. By flooding the reactor cavity where the RPV is immersed, the external face of the vessel is cooled, and corium is maintained inside the lower head. The overall phenomenology occurring during the IVMR in an iPWR is similar to the phenomenology in a high-power LWR, but a few differences can be highlighted due to the different design features. Among the differences, it is interesting to notice that the molten pool is rather shallow and does not occupy a full hemisphere. This has an impact on the heat flux profile along the vessel wall. Another difference is the rather thick oxide crust, for which the modelling approach is adapted with respect to what is usually done for the analysis of high-power reactors. The purpose of this paper is to develop a 0D model for the steady-state analysis of idealized cases in an iPWR. It has been developed in the framework of the SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom project. It is part of the preliminary activities of Work Package 4, which examines the evaluation of the safety margin for several existing iPWR designs, considering available data and plausible assumptions for the unknown parameters. The aim of this model is to include the specific features of iPWRs and provide first estimates of safety margins. Heat transfer correlations depending on the aspect ratio H/R are used to consider the shallow geometry of the pool. The absence of a designed channel or baffle around the vessel requires the use of pool boiling correlations for the external cooling. This work will also prepare the next steps of SASPAM-SA, which is the identification of models in SA codes needing some improvements. Integral reactor calculations focused on the IVMR are also planned: they will be compared to the results of the present 0D approach. Finally, we mention that the developed model is not design specific: it may be easily adapted to various designs by changing some geometrical or material parameters. The 0D model was implemented in Python. This tool will be made available for other partners for applications to other designs of interest.

KEYWORDS

SMR, SA, IVMR, Integral PWR, SASPAM-SA

1 INTRODUCTION

Climate change implications, growing energy demand, and the present emphasis on energy safety and independence have sparked a renewed interest in nuclear energy and more sophisticated reactor designs. Small Modular Reactors (SMR) are one of the most viable options for the deployment of the next generation reactors [1]. They seek to achieve the major objectives of higher inherent safety and enhanced economic efficiency by contemporarily cutting capital costs and building times. Among SMRs, integral Pressurized Water Reactors (iPWR) stand out and seem very attractive since based on the previous generation Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology. Their key aspects are the relatively low electrical power output, a Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) integral design and the installation of many passive safety systems. Among the possible safety procedures needed to mitigate Severe Accident (SA) scenarios, In Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR) has been studied thoroughly in the context of High-Power Reactors (HPR). Indeed, many designs share the application of IVMR, like the AP1000 [2] and the HPR1000 [3]. This strategy is also very captivating for iPWR, whose analyses are being carried out in the framework of the Horizon Europe - Euratom Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident (SASPAM-SA) project [4] [5], coordinated by ENEA (Italy). Among its major goals, SASPAM-SA aims to determine plausible postulated SA scenarios for iPWRs¹, to examine the applicability of existing experimental databases to iPWRs and to identify gaps of knowledge needed to be filled with new experiments. Other key objectives are: the evaluation of the capability of state-of-the-art international computational tools to reproduce the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios; the prediction of the radiological impact on and off-site, considering special SA mitigation and management strategies. Two generic iPWR designs are considered in the project², named Design 1 and Design 2. The iPWR Design 1 is a 160 MWth natural-circulation PWR with a compact steam generator and a submerged containment, in a large pool of borated water. Design 2 on the other hand has a thermal power of around 1000 MWth, a dry spherical containment, and utilizes several passive systems for accident protection. Both designs share similar layouts within the RPV and SA mitigation, based on IVMR strategy. In the SASPAM-SA Work Package 4, coordinated by IRSN, the IVMR is investigated considering both Design 1 and 2. As part of the overall research effort, a 0D model has first been developed by the Nuclear Engineering Research Group of Sapienza University of Rome, in collaboration with IRSN, for the steady state analysis of IVMR in iPWRs. The purpose of this 0D model is to identify specificities of iPWRs with respect to HPRs in terms of IVMR configurations and make available to the partners a fast-running tool giving the magnitude of expected results for a wide range of steady state configurations. It will be useful for identification and definition of model improvements in SA codes. It will also provide references for comparison with SA codes, also

¹ Advanced designs, as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a severe accident sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to severe accidents need to be postulated and deterministically studied. More detailed information's in [6].

² To maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project, two generic design-concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with larger operating reactor, have been selected for the analyses. These two generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR. It is not the project's objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favored designs under postulated SA condition. No PSA considerations will be done in the project due to the generic nature of the reactor concept considered, then the scenarios identified will be characterized in terms of severity but not in terms of probability.

planned within this project, in which transient effects will have to be considered. This paper is focused on the description of the 0D model, in particular its methodology and assumptions, together with its preliminary results and identification of specificities of iPWRs compared to HPRs.

2 IVMR 0D MODEL

The 0D model is composed of various modules and considers a steady state configuration of corium in the lower plenum. Its main purpose is to provide quantitative elements to identify the most relevant parameters and phenomena that should be investigated further with integral reactor calculations. During a SA scenario, core and vessel internals melt and relocate at the bottom of the RPV. The model deals with a stabilized phase after a transient evolution when a stratified two-phase liquid pool is formed.

2.1 Thermochemical Module and Corium properties

2.1.1 Thermochemical Module and densities

The main constituents of the stratified pool are Uranium (U), Zirconium (Zr), Oxygen (O) and steel (Fe). Two phases are present: an oxidic one composed by Zr and U oxides and a metallic one made up by elemental U, Zr and Fe [7][8]. Their equilibrium compositions are needed to compute their densities and thermophysical properties. To achieve that, the analytical model from [9] has been considered. It is based on three assumptions: oxygen is present only in a bounded state inside the oxide pool, Fe presence in the oxide pool is neglected and the ratio of U to Zr atoms remains unchanged in oxide and metal pools after separation. The inputs given to this module are the molten masses of fuel, Zirconium, and steel internals. Then, it computes the initial U/Zr and Fe/Zr atomic ratios and the Zr degree of oxidation, labeled C_{ox} . The model outputs are the molar fractions of every species in both pools, which are used to compute the pools volumes, masses, densities and thermal properties. The oxide and liquid metal pools relative positions strongly affects the IVMR heat transfer problem. For this reason, the relative densities were estimated to precisely identify the region of existence of the pool disposition selected for the current 0D model (i.e., oxide pool below, Liquid Metal (LM) layer above) and to compare it with the parameter ranges of interest for the considered reactor design. This kind of analysis is generic, and it was repeated for different reactor layouts, i.e., iPWR Design 1 and Design 2 of SASPAM-SA project and a generic PWR of 1000 MW_e as considered in [10], referred to High Power Reactor HPR in the rest of this paper. The input mass of steel (up to the maximum steel inventory corresponding to the complete melting of the core support plate) and the Zirconium degree of oxidation were varied, and the corresponding densities of oxide pool and LM layer were computed according to the thermochemical model presented above. The results are shown in Figure 1, where the lines of equal density are shown for the three aforementioned designs³. Cases corresponding to a lighter LM layer are located above the curves. It may be seen that for the two iPWR designs, lower steel mass ratios are possible compared to HPR case, leading to situations where the heavy metal configuration (i.e., LM layer denser than the oxide pool) is the most probable. In addition, in Design 2, the UO₂/Zr mass ratio in the fuel rods is lower compared to Design1 and HPR and this leads to a lower density of the oxide phase. When this ratio is reduced, the density of the oxide phase becomes very close to the density of the LM layer, and it is more difficult to get a light metal. This explains why the Design 2 curve is above the two other designs in Figure 1. These preliminary considerations are based on the outcomes of equilibrium calculations only and they must be confirmed by transient integral code calculations. It may be concluded that, for the designs studied, stratification inversion is very likely to occur during the evolution of the molten pool in the lower plenum. This justifies the need of studying IVMR phenomenology further with dedicated transient codes able to simulate corium pool oxidation and transient steel addition. If densities of the two phases are very close, it may even be assumed that the molten pool is not stratified, and that metal and oxide phases are mixed. This will be done in the future steps of SASPAM-SA project.

³ Higher steel mass fractions may be obtained for design 1 and for HPR (up to 0.8) and are not represented since those situations will lead to light metal layer formation even for low Zr oxidation degree.

Figure 1: Pools iso-density lines for the considered reactor designs.

2.1.2 Corium properties

The LM layer and oxide pool thermal properties are computed according to formulas and correlations available in [8]. Except for the viscosity, every property is computed as a weighted average, with the weight varying for each property: for density the weight is the volumetric fraction, for thermal conductivity it is the molar fraction, for heat capacity it is the mass fraction. A more accurate discussion on the pool properties can be found in [8]. Finally, this module distributes the decay power in the oxide pool and in the LM layer, based on the atomic Uranium content, derived from the molar fractions yielded by the previous calculations.

2.2 Geometrical Module

An accurate evaluation of the system's geometry is crucial for the overall reliability of the code since the layers' shapes (i.e., height over diameter) strongly influence the heat transfer calculations and power flow paths. In the reference scenario considered, the oxide pool lies at the bottom of the Lower Head (LH), while the metal layer lies on top of it. The overall system is depicted in Figure 2. Further considerations on this aspect are present in section 1.1. For the metal layer geometry, the module considers the partial ablation of the vessel thickness due to the focusing effect (labeled ΔR in Figure 2). In addition, the presence of the crust inside the oxide pool is also considered. It is assumed that both elements (pool and crust) have the same atomic composition. The purpose of the geometrical module is to evaluate the height of both pools and to calculate the ablated vessel thickness while doing so. This is achieved through a system of 3 equations in 3 unknowns, reported below, that has been obtained considering the geometrical formulas of the spherical cap. The unknowns in the system are h_{oxy} , h and ΔR which represent respectively the height of the oxide pool, the total combined height, and the ablated vessel thickness. All the volumes in Eq.s (1), (2) and (3) are input data and can be assessed starting from the outputs of the thermochemical model, i.e., layers' masses and densities. Moreover, combining the height of both pools, the geometrical module evaluates Θ_p , the angle identifying the top of the pool as illustrated in Figure 2, which will be used in the heat transfer module (see next section).

$$V_{oxy} = \pi h_{oxy}^2 \left(R_{LH} - \frac{h_{oxy}}{3} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$V_{lm} - V_{ablated} + V_{oxy} = \pi h^2 \left(R_{LH} - \frac{h}{3} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\left\{ \pi (h + \Delta R)^2 \left[(R_{LH} + \Delta R) - \frac{(h + \Delta R)}{3} \right] \right\} - \left\{ \pi (h_{oxy} + \Delta R)^2 \left[(R_{LH} + \Delta R) - \frac{(h_{oxy} + \Delta R)}{3} \right] \right\} = V_{lm} \quad (3)$$

Figure 2: Lower Head schematization for the geometric module.

2.3 Heat Transfer Module

The heat transfer module has been developed starting from models and considerations presented in [10][8]. As already discussed, the reference scenario considers the oxide pool surrounded by an oxidic crust. The interface between these two elements is assumed to be at the oxide liquidus temperature. The latter, which is one of the boundary conditions for the problem, is postulated to be equal to 2800 K, according to the indications provided by [11]. The liquid metal layer on the other hand finds itself on top of the oxidic one, and for these analyses a top radiative boundary condition has been chosen. The radiative heat transfer mode has been selected following the results of the preliminary calculations, reported in section 3. They hint that, for the iPWR design considered, the metal layer is very thin with a height of around 15 cm. As stated by [12], for a thin liquid metal layer the adiabatic condition becomes very conservative. For this, the radiative heat transfer has been included in the module. Surrounding the lower head there is the water flooded cavity, which is assumed to be at saturation temperature for conservative reasons. The heat transfer module is conceptually divided into three steps: evaluation of the oxide pool bulk temperature, power balance in the oxide pool and power balance in the LM pool. The first step requires the evaluation of the internal Rayleigh number (Ra) of the oxide pool, and the evaluation of the Nusselt number in the upward (Nu_{up}) and downward (Nu_{dn}) directions. Many correlations derived from experimental facilities are available in literature. In this model, the focus has been on the ones that possess the dependence on the aspect ratio of the oxide pool (H/R) for the downward heat transfer. Also, only correlations deriving from experiments considering the hemispherical geometry have been selected. The correlations have the following form:

$$Nu_{dn} = ARa^a \left(\frac{H}{R}\right)^b \quad (4)$$

$$Nu_{up} = BRa^c \quad (5)$$

The coefficients vary for each correlation, and they are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 : Heat transfer correlations implemented to evaluate the oxide pool thermal transfer.

Correlation	A	a	B	B	C	Ra_{min}	Ra_{max}
ACOPO [8]	0.1857	0.2304	0.25	2.4415	0.1772	1.00E+13	1.00E+17
BALI 2D [13]	0.116	0.25	0.32	0.383	0.233	1.00E+13	1.00E+17
BALI3D [13]	0.131	0.25	0.19	0.383	0.233	1.00E+13	1.00E+17
Mini ACOPO [14]	0.0038	0.35	0.25	1.95	0.18	1.00E+11	7.00E+14
ASFIA [15]	0.54	0.2	0.25	0.403	0.226	2.00E+10	1.10E+14

After determining the Nu numbers for both directions, to get the oxide pool temperature (T_{pool}), the expression below is adopted. It accounts for the repartition of the total residual decay power (P_{res}). For SASPAM-SA design 2, this latter parameter has been derived from [16] and it is approximately 4.4 MW:

$$T_{pool} = T_{liq} + P_{res} \frac{H}{k_{ox}} (Nu_{dn} S_{dn} + Nu_{up} S_{up})^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Where the height H^4 and the downward (S_{dn}) and upward (S_{up}) surfaces are computed by the geometrical module. Once the temperature of the oxide pool is found, the model moves on to evaluate the thermal field along the LH section in contact with the oxide pool itself, and to estimate the crust's thickness. The LH region contacting the oxide pool is divided into N polar regions, over which the heat balance will be solved. For the most relevant parameters notation, refer to Figure 3.

Figure 3 : 0D model Heat transfer visual schematization.

For the heat balance of each polar region, a spherical one-dimensional conduction problem is solved. The formulas to be implemented are derived from [17]. This allows for a better representation of the LH actual geometry and thermal field. The heat flux profile in the downwards direction and the correlation to be used to assess the Critical Heat Flux (CHF) for the cavity water have been selected from literature [13][14][15][18]. The former is used to distribute the average heat flux in the downwards direction (that can be derived reverting Eq. 6 once T_{pool} is known) along the polar coordinate, computing $\phi_{dn}(\theta)$, which is a boundary condition for the conduction problem. The distribution is based on weights calculated by considering the LH internal surface associated with each polar mesh. The selected experimental internal heat flux profiles have different shapes but all increase as the polar coordinate approaches the top of the pool. The evaluation of the water CHF, which is achieved through Cheung correlation [18], is crucial to determine the heat transfer mode to be used to compute the associated heat transfer coefficient (HTC, h_w), that is another boundary condition to the conduction problem. If the heat flux to the external water is lower than the CHF, nucleate pool boiling is assumed at the LH external surface and Rohsenow correlation [19] is used for the heat transfer coefficient. Instead, if the heat flux exceeds the CHF, film pool boiling regime is assumed and Bromley correlation is adopted [20]. The resulting system of equations that is solved for each θ coordinate along the vessel is:

⁴ It should be noted that H corresponds to the height of the liquid part of the oxide pool and is thus dependent on the results of the heat transfer evaluation allowing to estimate the crust thicknesses. Thus, calculations are repeated in an iterative way until all the parameters involved converge (i.e., relative differences are below the selected tolerances).

$$\varphi_{dn}(\theta) - \frac{k_c}{\delta_{c,dn}} (T_{liq} - T_{in}) \left(\frac{R_{LH}}{R_{LH} - \delta_{c,dn}} \right) + \frac{q'''_c}{2} \delta_{c,dn} \left(1 + \frac{\delta_{c,dn}}{3(R_{LH} - \delta_{c,dn})} \right) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{k_v}{\delta_v} (T_{in} - T_{out}) \frac{R_{LH,ext}}{R_{LH}} - \frac{k_c}{\delta_{c,dn}} (T_{liq} - T_{in}) \left(1 - \frac{\delta_{c,dn}}{R_{LH}} \right) - \frac{q'''_c}{2} \delta_{c,dn} \left(1 - \frac{\delta_{c,dn}}{3R_{LH}} \right) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{k_v}{\delta_v} (T_{in} - T_{out}) \frac{R_{LH}}{R_{LH,ext}} - h_w (T_{out} - T_{sat}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Where R_{LH} and $R_{LH,ext}$ represent the internal and external vessel radiuses, δ_v the vessel thickness, $\delta_{c, dn}$ the crust thickness, q'''_c the volumetric power inside the crust, which is equal to the oxide pool one since we assumed the same composition for both. The thermal conductivities for the oxidic crust and the vessel (k_c and k_v) are estimated through extrapolation functions derived from [8]. The unknowns in Eq.s (7), (8) and (9), are the crust thickness in the downward direction $\delta_{c, dn}$, and the LH internal and external temperatures T_{in} , T_{out} . At the current stage, the model does not assume vessel wall ablation in front of the Oxide crust. Once the system is solved, the model checks if the total power in the downwards direction corresponds to the sum of the power transmitted through every polar coordinate. For the metal layer heat balance, as already mentioned, a top radiative boundary condition has been selected, with a metal layer emissivity of 0.38 [10] and an average core internal structures temperature of 1100 K. This last value comes from MELCOR preliminary integral calculations performed in SASPAM-SA and related to Design 2. It is not to be considered as a definitive value since the overall simulation activity is in progress. To solve the heat balance, a non-linear system of 9 equations and 9 unknowns has been derived. In this case, in first approximation, only a single polar coordinate is considered. For this, a one-dimensional slab approach has been selected to solve the conduction problem in the vessel. The implemented formulas are reported below:

$$F_{dn} = h_{dn} (T_{m,bot} - T_m) \quad (10)$$

$$F_{up} = h_{up} (T_m - T_{m,top}) \quad (11)$$

$$F_{up} = \varepsilon \sigma (T_{m,top}^4 - T_{str}^4) \quad (12)$$

$$F_w = h_{wall} (T_m - T_{in}) \quad (13)$$

$$F_w = \frac{k_v}{\delta_v} (T_{in} - T_{out}) \quad (14)$$

$$F_w = h_w (T_{out} - T_{sat}) \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi_{up} = \frac{k_c}{\delta_{c,up}} (T_{liq} - T_{m,bot}) - \frac{q'''_c}{2} \delta_{c,up} \quad (16)$$

$$F_{dn} = \frac{k_c}{\delta_{c,up}} (T_{liq} - T_{m,bot}) + \frac{q'''_c}{2} \delta_{c,up} \quad (17)$$

$$F_{dn} S_{dn} + q'''_m V_m = F_{up} S_{up} + F_w S_w \quad (18)$$

The unknowns in Eqns (10) to (18) are: the metal layer heat fluxes in the downwards (F_{dn}), upwards (F_{up}), and lateral (i.e., wall, F_w) directions; the metal layer pool temperature (T_m); the metal layer bottom ($T_{m,bot}$) and top ($T_{m,top}$) surfaces temperatures; the oxide crust upwards thickness ($\delta_{c,up}$); the vessel external temperature (T_{out}). The heat transfer module also calculates the residual thickness of the vessel (δ_v). An outer iteration is thus performed between the various models presented so far (i.e., thermochemical, geometrical and heat transfer) until the δ_v computed allows to obtain a vessel internal temperature (T_{in}) equal to the vessel's melting temperature (set to 1600 K according to [8]). The heat transfer mode assumed for the metal layer is natural convection. The Rayleigh number is used to compute the heat transfer coefficients in three directions: upwards (h_{up}), downwards (h_{dn}) and through the vessel wall (h_{wall}). Globe-Dropkin correlation [21] is selected for the first two directions, while for the latter, Chawla-Chan correlation has been chosen [22].

2.3.1 Influence of the oxide pool aspect ratio H/R

As previously hinted, one of the criteria for the correlations selection for oxide downwards heat transfer, is the dependance on the oxide pool aspect ratio. The influence of this parameter on the power repartition is depicted in Figure 4. On the y-axis we have the fraction of the oxide total power that goes in the upwards direction X_{up} , computed for each correlation, while on the x-axis lies the oxide pool aspect ratio. The black dotted vertical lines represent the test cases discussed in this paper. The calculations for X_{up} are performed using average corium properties, otherwise the aspect ratio would not have been an independent parameter. The curves are cut considering the Ra validity range for each correlation (see Table 1). This evaluation highlights that for decreasing oxide pool aspect ratio, regardless of the used correlation, X_{up} increases. Higher X_{up} deviations are observed for low H/R values, while the correlations are more consistent at high aspect ratios. The increase in upwards heat flux is clearly more relevant for iPWR with respect to HPR, since the former present shallower oxide pools, hence a higher upwards surface area with respect to the downwards one. In this paper, the BALI-3D correlation was used.

Figure 4: Oxide pool aspect ratio influence on power partitioning.

3 SIMULATION RESULTS

3.1 Verification Case (HPR)

Firstly, to assess the appropriateness of the developed 0D model, it was tested with the steady state case studied in the IVMR benchmark [10]. The detailed inputs and results are not presented here but preliminary results well reproduce the benchmark results of [10]. The most important difference is the heat flux from the LM layer to the vessel wall, which is higher in the 0D model case. This is because the geometrical model does not consider the LH geometry transition from hemispherical to cylindrical shape. Indeed, it has been developed expecting shallow pools in iPWR. So, the height of metal is underestimated for this HPR case.

3.2 Input data for the application to iPWR cases.

Once verified the suitability of the 0D model, preliminary calculations corresponding to the SASPAM-SA Design 1 and 2 have been performed, whose input data are reported in Table 2. Note that the masses data refer to the initial masses which are supposed to be later molten during degradation.

Table 2: Input parameters for the 0D model test cases

PARAMETER	UNITS	SASPAM-SA Design 2 [23]	SASPAM-SA Design 1
LH radius	m	3.11	1.4
LH thickness	m	0.25	0.12
LH height	m	1.27	0.7
UO ₂ mass	tons	58	9
Zr mass	tons	19.4	2.5
Steel mass	tons	22.2	4
C _{ox} (Zr oxidation degree)	-	0.70	0.45
Decay power	MW	4.4	1.7
Core structure temperature	K	1100	1100
Metal emissivity	-	0.38	0.38

3.3 Results and comparison of designs

The main results for the two iPWR designs are summarized in Table 3. The partitioning of the overall decay heat (see Table 2) among the different elements constituting the stabilized phases is presented in Figure 5, and compared to the HPR case [10].

Table 3: Main results associated with the Design 1 and 2 test cases.

PARAMETER	UNITS	DESIGN 2	DESIGN 1
Oxide superheating	K	36.4	43.9
Metal superheating	K	26.	50.
Average $\delta_{c, dn}$	cm	6.5	4.4
Residual Vessel thickness in LM layer	cm	22.1	8.7
Radiative power fraction in LM layer	-	0.872	0.662
Power to LM layer fraction in liquid oxide	-	0.657	0.655
Heat flux from LM layer to vessel (F_w)	MW/m ²	0.133	0.335
Oxide layer H/R	-	0.28	0.33
LM layer H/R	-	0.09	0.146

Figure 5: Distribution of the overall decay power between the main volumes.

As visible, in all the considered reactor designs most of the power is generated within the molten oxide pool (more than 60%). However, in iPWR designs a significant fraction is also produced within the oxide crust

(above 11%). In Design 2, where a high oxidation degree of the Zr (70%) is considered, this fraction is even comparable to the one corresponding to the LM layer (13%). On the contrary, in the HPR design, the contribution of the oxide crusts is negligible. The comparison of the oxide crust profiles is presented in Figure 6. At the top of the oxide pool the crust thickness is about 4-5 cm in both iPWR design, whereas it is about 0.5 cm in a typical existing PWR. In Design 2, a thick crust of more than 14 cm is evaluated at the bottom of the pool, due to the very large vessel radius related to this reactor layout (cf. Table 2).

Figure 6: Profile of crust thickness around the oxide pool.

The power fraction transferred the top of the oxide pool (i.e. to the metal layer) is about 66% in both iPWR designs (see Table 3), which is much higher than the value corresponding to a typical existing high-power PWR (50%). This is due to the very low value of the oxide pool aspect ratio, as explained in the previous section (cf. Figure 4). In Figure 7, the relative contributions of the different power flow paths are compared. Referring to the LM layer, the fraction of power lost by radiative heat transfer is quite large in iPWR designs compared to HPR: between 34% and 51% of the total power vs 13% in HPR. Also in this case, this is due to the very low value of the LM layer aspect ratio (see Table 3). This leads to a very large ratio between the top flat surface and the lateral surface of the metal. Consequently, the focusing effect is limited and the level of maximum heat flux is lower than the predicted CHF at all angles along the vessel. The minimum residual vessel thicknesses are evaluated equal to 22 cm for Design 2 and 9 cm in Design 1, which is comparable to the VVER440 case (about 10cm). Much lower values (2-3cm) are obtained for a typical high-power reactor.

Figure 7: Relative extent of the different power flow paths leaving the global system.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the framework of SASPAM-SA project WP4, a 0D model for steady state IVMR was developed, with the aim of identifying the necessary model improvements and providing preliminary estimates for integral reactor codes users. Its development was first made for iPWRs at the current stage. Two designs were studied in this paper. The model was also assessed by comparison to a high-power PWR benchmark case. As expected, the first results show that in-vessel retention strategy appears feasible, with a good safety margin. However, detailed data and complete calculations would be necessary to go further. Some specific features of IVMR in iPWRs appear: a larger fraction of power transferred to the top of the oxide pool because of the low aspect ratio (shallow pool), the existence of a rather thick oxide crust and the occurrence of a thin metal layer but a limited focusing effect because of a large fraction of power lost by radiative heat transfer. Also, it is expected that, in many cases, density inversion would occur in transient conditions, starting with a heavy metal. It may even be possible to have a well-mixed pool instead of stratification. Regarding the oxide crust thickness, results yield average values of one order of magnitude higher than for HPR. All these specific features have to be considered in models. The impact of aspect ratio H/R can be treated by simply selecting correlations which already include the H/R parameter, and some of those correlations are listed in the paper. The presence of thick oxide crusts requires a modification of existing models which usually neglect the crust. A model was proposed in the paper. The existence of a heavy metal layer at the beginning of the transient, leading to a stratification inversion, is a more difficult issue: first it requires a heat transfer model for the heavy metal layer (such model was not developed yet) and second it requires a transient calculation of stratification inversion, which is not available in all system codes. Finally, a more accurate analysis of top radiative heat transfer must be done as it appears to be significant for the evaluation of focusing effect and the maximum heat flux to the vessel. Some of those issues will be addressed in the next steps of SASPAM-SA WP4, by developed new models and/or performing transient calculations of the stratified pool.

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